

Personal Finance: Goals, Approach and Controlling

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ABSTRACT

Personal Finance means managing your own money, including saving, investing, budgeting, insurance, banking, mortgages, retirement planning, real estate, and tax planning. In short, they are the approaches and goals of an individual for planning their long term and short term financial needs. Saving and controlling is a battle between spending now or later or then saving for the future. This literature review has shown that budgeting, managing liquidity, and financial efficacy are essential elements of personal economic behaviour. It would be a good idea to instil the principles of personal finance management at a younger age group via relevant financial management courses.

KEYWORDS: Personal Finance; Budgeting; Liquidity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Personal Finance means managing your own money, including saving, investing, budgeting, insurance, banking, mortgages, retirement planning, real estate, and tax planning. In short, they are the approaches and goals of an individual for planning their long term and short term financial needs. The planning can be done based on the money earned, expenditures, the standard of living, etc.

The most significant prerequisite for personal finance is setting up for a retirement income. With the increasing cost of living, better life expectancy rates, significantly higher for women, and rising healthcare costs, a substantial fund needs to be set aside, including provision for unforeseen events (Redhead, 2008).

The valuation of personal financial needs can be done by self or with the help of a financial advisor, and it is based on four CORE principles: Circumstance (income, age, assets and liabilities, and family structure and responsibilities); Objectives (liquidity, high rate of returns, investments to provide income but "never touch the capital"); Risk (market risk, income risk, capital risk); Expenditure (Saving and control) (Redhead, 2008). Saving and controlling is a battle between spending now or later or then saving for the future. Individuals who are prone to control their expenditures are more successful with their savings which becomes an automatic habit and is not dependent on their willpower. It would be a good idea to have this money transferred to a separate saving account, further boosting this habit. The issue is that many people cannot make the correct financial choices due to a lack of knowledge and interest in that direction (Bernanke, 2001 and Bernard, 2010). Therefore this review plans to elucidate the different principles, goals, and approaches of financial management.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The approach to managing personal finance includes a financial plan based on five essential elements: Budgeting, Financial hefty purchases, Managing Liquidity, Long term investing, Insurance, Financial efficacy, etc. (Redhead, 2008).

2.1 Budgeting

Thaler (1999) has explained that budgeting as a personal finance element is based on the Mental Accounting theory, "the set of cognitive operations used by individuals and households to organize, evaluate and keep track of financial activities". Studies in America (Hogarth *et al.*, 2002) based on a national survey about financial management found that less than 46% of people had a budget and only thirty-six percent planned for future goals. Thirty-two percent prepared a written budget, used software (26%), and eighteen percent had the information in their heads (mental accounting).

The approach to improving this behaviour is to encourage mobile applications to keep track of their spending and accounts (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau, 2017).

2.2 Managing liquidity

Liquidity has cash in hand for everyday purchases like buying groceries, paying bills, emergency purposes. This money is easily accessible via debit cards, credit cards, etc. But the downside of this issue is that the rate of returns in liquid assets is less than shares and bonds that, in the long run, offer a higher rate of returns; therefore, it is not advisable to hold large amounts of money as liquid assets.

The younger generation between the age groups of 19 -29 years is an attractive segment to the banks to sell their products like credit cards, loans for education. Credit options, etc. After graduation, poor financial choices, especially after taking huge educational loans, could have several negative consequences for young people. Financially illiterate graduates might be dealing with various financial matters such as bankruptcy, mortgage crises, or financial fraud.

Therefore the need to have knowledge and discipline about managing liquidity inculcated among the younger generation is to avoid concerns with bankruptcy, financial frauds, and mortgage issues in the future. This can be accomplished by teaching principles of financial literacy (Altintas, 2011).

Students should be encouraged to take financial education courses to teach them the principles of discounting (to choose between immediate and delayed outcomes while making expenditures) (Redhead, 2008).

Furthermore, if one needs to buy something costly like a car; holiday, the money has to be generated by either borrowing or savings. It is imperative as far as possible not to keep too much liquid cash till the acquisitions are made as then the savings will produce more interest than just liquid money at home. The next best option is to keep them in short term deposits or short maturity market instruments like debt funds (Redhead, 2008).

2.3 Long term Investment

Long term investment ranges from making provision for retirement, buying a house, education loans for children, or passing on property to legal heirs. The golden rule for long term investment is to start saving one-third of one's income early in their career life. Over the years, the net rate of return on one's investment is calculated based on taxation and inflation. This can be achieved mainly through investing in shares which has an element of risk but fairly good returns with the principle of compounding interest with the long-term investments (Redhead, 2008).

2.4 Insurance & Endowment Policy

Planning finances is not just taxing and investments. It is also about appraising funds in hand, emergency funds, having a varied investment assortment, and planning for insurance requirements. In short, it is saving oneself and family against financial losses for unprecedented events. Insurance comes in different forms for different needs, for example, insurance for life; disability; family health care; individual healthcare, accident; death, etc.

An endowment policy is a variant of saving strategy and attached life insurance. The money is invested for about twenty years from regular payments every month, which funds insurance cover and contributes to the investment fund.

2.5 Financial Self-Efficacy

Financial management calls for efficacy which, as explained by Bandura (1994), Bandura (2006), and Gecas(1989), is a person's sense of self-agency due to a belief that they can accomplish their tasks and deal with life's challenges. In other words, a self-assured person manages the financial investments and challenges sensibly and does not avoid threats associated with financial management. A study done by Farrel *et al.* (2015) has explored the concept of financial self-efficacy among women

in Australia and found that financial self-efficacy was one of the most important predictors of the kind of financial products preferred by women. Women preferred savings, mortgages and investments and less debt related products. The study also found that predictors like being better educated; partnership status; age; household income; having taken a financial management course; possessing a bank account as a teenager were positively associated with better money management, and a bad childhood experience with money was more likely to make the person depend more on loans for their needs. Women who were more risk-oriented had a higher propensity to own credit cards, and less risk-oriented had a radical proclivity towards a savings account. It was also found that possessing more financial products signifies the individual's tendency to diversify risk and better economic well-being (Farrell, 2016).

2.6 Key observations from the review:

- Budgeting is essential with limited resources, but it is placed at the lesser end of the behavioural pyramid by most individuals (Xiao and O'Neil, 2018).
- The other issues with financial arrangements are Inflexible decision making while allocating expenses, inaccuracy, impractical budget preparation and execution (Xiao and O'Neil, 2018).
- Gauge the current financial situation and plan accordingly, i.e. money available (Kireeva, 2016).
- Insurance is necessary to save oneself from risk and unanticipated economic issues (Kireeva, 2016).
- Take help from a financial expert to put a plan together, including setting up a savings account, plan future investments, retirement plan in place, and appropriate insurance planning (Kireeva, 2016).
- Constant adjustment and re-evaluation of the financial plan is necessary (Kireeva, 2016).
- Risks associated with a savings account are ten percent, hedge funds about 20%, and stock about fifteen percent (Kireeva, 2016).
- Individuals' risk-taking tendencies depend upon price sensitivity and their assessment of the cost-benefit ratio of the financial products (Farrell, 2016).

3. CONCLUSION

This literature review has shown that budgeting, managing liquidity, and financial efficacy are essential elements of personal economic behaviour. It would be a good idea to instil the principles of personal finance management at a younger age group via relevant financial management courses. Knowledge of personal finance increases chances of better financial management, leading to efficiency in the working of savings and investments. It is not a one-time exercise. It should be taught as a part of an everyday lifestyle.

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